

Some combinatorial aspects related to low dimensional manifolds via crystal patterns

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Abstract— Combinatorial features on manifolds are first seen in the description of crystallographic groups. We use this connection to describe discretizations for a class of manifolds in light of possible applications to naturally occurring surfaces. In this paper we consider tessellations on smooth orientable manifolds arising out of certain group actions. The goal is to find appropriate notions in the language of discrete structures to describe the underlying geometry. As a primary motivation a continuous family of lattices on Riemann surfaces is considered. Discrete groups are seen as the central objects in describing various discrete structures on manifolds. Further certain applications have been described.

Keywords— tessellations, discretizations, Riemann, crystal, manifold

I. INTRODUCTION

Triangulations, quadrangulations and more general cell decompositions of surfaces and higher dimensional manifolds are studied quite often to get a combinatorial viewpoint of underlying geometric spaces. In the context of map-mapping Gauss understood curvature from a combinatorial point of view. More recently authors like R. A. Duke considered such combinatorial issues in the setting of submanifolds in \mathbf{R}^n . Our interest in studying discrete structures on geometric spaces is motivated by quantization procedures in aspects underlying theoretical physics. Further it is found that in computational geometry and geometric modeling ‘discrete structures’ on manifolds play a central role. In literature there is no consensus on what is the right definition of discretization of a manifold. But when one looks at the traditional usage of the word discretization we note that in numerical analysis domains in \mathbf{R}^n or rather submanifolds of \mathbf{R}^n are discretized by integral grids. We consider tessellations of Riemann surfaces and look at various connections to combinatorial mathematics with a view towards applications. From an aesthetic viewpoint we also look at certain generalizations for surfaces and other geometric spaces.

The idea of identifying a smooth surface with a discrete analogue is very much similar to Wierstrass’ idea of approximating any continuous function to a polynomial. Hermann Minkowski in his treatise on the geometry of numbers wanted to model geometric regions using lattice points. The above mentioned points lead us to some studies where discrete structures are defined on an underlying topological space. In crystallography point groups are seen to be acting on appropriate Euclidean spaces. This notion has been extended to hyperbolic model spaces and hence related crystallographic structures have been studied..

One imagines a crystal space as an interlocking system of molecules that can be continued indefinitely in any direction filling up all space. To quote Hiller[8] "the essential feature that a mathematical treatment of crystals should abstract is the existence of a small chunk of the crystal pattern which acts as a building

block for the whole structure". This motivates consideration of tessellation of the Euclidean space and further generalizations. At an elementary level a tessellation can be defined as the covering of the surface with a repeating unit consisting of one or more shapes such that there is no space in between and there is no overlapping of shapes.

Similarly in crystallographic studies symmetrical patterns have been explored extensively. In two dimensional topology only 17 distinct possible crystallographic patterns have been shown to be existing. This result is couched in the language of abstract groups and hence this topic falls in the area of algebraic topology. One observes a centre and a line about which mirror symmetry exists. A combination of translations, reflections and glide reflections lead to lattice group actions. Analogously we have a result in 3-dimensional spaces that there are exactly 23 topologically distinct tessellated polyhedra.

Now tessellations have been understood for the Euclidean plane and also in some cases for the non-Euclidean setting at least in dimension-2. After the plane one can look at 2-dimensional manifolds i.e surfaces of certain kind and understand their tessellations. For instance geodesic triangles can be used to tessellate the sphere. Thus our geometric interest leads us to the universe of smooth manifolds.

We roughly define a discrete structure on a smooth manifold as a discrete set of points, with additional structure in the context of either algebraic number theory or a combinatorial structure like a group, groupoid, lattice, simplicial, complexes. In this section we look at orientable surfaces and discuss properties of group actions.

We have seen that crystallography has a group theoretic connotation. Here we look at the related aspect of tessellations..

Definition(1.1)

A tessellation of a plane Π which is either the Euclidean plane E^2 or the hyperbolic plane H^2 is a subdivision of the plane into polygonal tiles.

On one hand Hilbert's question asks for identification of point groups that describe crystallography of spaces of constant curvature and on the other one can look at the related aspect of tessellations in a group theoretic setting.

A tessellation of a plane Π which is either the euclidean plane or the hyperbolic plane is a subdivision of the plane into polygonal shapes or tiles a_i such that

i] All tiles are of the same shape. i.e if a_i and a_j are two tiles then there exists an isometric transformation T such that T takes a_i to a_j .

ii] Given a_i, a_j distinct tiles either $a_i \cap a_j = \{\}$

or $a_i \cap a_j = p$ where $\{p\}$ is a single point in Π or $a_i \cap a_j$ is a common edge of the two tiles.

Group theoretic aspects:

If T is a tessellation of polygons a_i then there exists a group of isometries Γ acting on Π such that the fundamental regions of the group action coincides with a unit tile of the tessellation.

Definition(1.2)

Let Γ act on a space X . Then

The orbit of x in X is defined as $Orb[H(x)] = \{ \Gamma(x) : x \text{ is in } \Pi \}$.

A point p in X is a limit point of x under Γ if for all open neighbourhoods U of y , U contains an infinite number of images of x .

Note that this definition implies, if x is a limit point for some h in Γ and if h has an infinite order then x is a limit point.

Definition(1.3)

(Discontinuous group action): A group action is said to be discontinuous if for all x in Π there exists no limit point of x in Π .

Proposition(1.1) If T is a tessellation and $H = \text{Isom}(S)$ then the associated group G acts discontinuously on S .

Proof: First of all we shall define discontinuous actions of a group G on a surface S as those actions in which for all points of S there are no limit points of S under the action of G . Now let us suppose that G does not act in a discontinuous fashion. Then we shall arrive at a contradiction. Following is the argument. Now since G does not act discontinuously then there will be a limit point say l of x in S . Let U be an open set that describes a neighborhood of l . Also let $k(U)$ be the number of tiles in the tessellation T such that they share points with U and choose U so that k is the minimum i.e, if l is in the interior of a tile then $k(U) = 1$, if l is on an edge of a tile then $k(U) = 2$ and if l is a node of a tile then $k(u) = n$ for n a finite integer greater than 2. Because l is a limit point, U contains an infinite number of images of x , and because U shares points with only a finite number of faces or tiles, there is at least one tile, F , which contains an infinite number of images of x . Consider G restricted only to those isometries which are symmetries of F say G^l .

$$G^l(F) = \{g \in G \mid G(F) = F \text{ where } F \text{ is a tile of the tessellation } T\}$$

Clearly G^l is of finite order and clearly any two points $x, x' \in F$ which are images under G are also images under $G^l(F)$. This is a contradiction since one cannot have infinite number of images for a group of finite order. Hence we proved that the action of G has to be of discontinuous type.

Remark(1.1) One can interpret discontinuous actions in the sense that each orbit $\Gamma(x)$ is locally finite. Since we are interested in tessellating curved surfaces and higher generalisations we discuss in the following section a prominent result in Surface theory. To effectively use the above mentioned group theoretic aspects we work in the class of 1-dimensional complex manifolds which are called Riemann surfaces.

Suppose X is a Riemann surface. This means that X is a 1-dimensional complex manifold. According to the Uniformization theorem we have the following:

Theorem(1.1)

The Riemann Surface X is biholomorphically equivalent to one of the following:

- 1) The extended complex plane \mathbb{C}
- 2) The complex plane \mathbb{C} .
- 3) The complex tori $\mathbb{C}/\mathbb{Z} + \mathbb{Z}$
- 4) The quotient of the upper half plane of the form $\Gamma \backslash \mathbb{H}$

The above mentioned result leads to some nice tessellations of any nice surfaces. By a nice surface we mean smooth orientable two-dimensional manifold. The complex structure alluded to earlier can be arrived at by putting isothermal coordinates. By a well known theory initiated by C.F.Gauss any orientable surface can be complexified by introducing isothermal coordinates [14]. Hence we delve into deeper aspects of Riemann surface theory and associated group actions.

Looking at the above classification one can already describe a natural class of tessellations on each of the above model spaces. The extended plane or the so called Riemann sphere can be tessellated by the action of the Lie group $SO(3)$.

There is a standard theory that the plane can be tessellated only by regular n -gons where $n=3, 4$ and 6 . In the second case the equivalence classes of the quotient group lead to square tilings while the third case leads to regular hexagonal tilings. Ofcourse the first case is that of equilateral triangles tessellating the plane. Note that we are interchangeably using the words tilings and tessellations. The fact that these are the only tessellations of the Euclidean plane by regular polygons is due to the following theorem

Theorem(1.2) The Euclidean plane \mathbf{E}^2 is tessellated by regular n -gons for $n=3, 4$ or 5 and these are the only possible tessellations of \mathbf{E}^2 by regular polygons.

Proof: Suppose \mathbf{E}^2 is tiled by a regular polygon with n -sides. Noticing any vertex 'v' in this tiled plane we see that the angles around v should add up to 360 degrees. Let χ denote any interior angle of our regular polygon. Since n is the number of sides we have $n\chi = 360$.

Hence for $n=3$ we get $\chi = 60$, and for $n=4$ we get $\chi = 90$.

To establish that only $n=3, 4$ and 6 are possible we turn the problem into a Diophantine equation. From the above analysis we see that $\frac{360}{\chi}$ must be a natural number since the ratio of 360 to magnitude of interior angle gives number of sides and this number must always be a natural number.

This means that after simplification we get $\frac{2n}{n-2}$ equals a number like 1,2,3 etc.

For $n=1$ or 2 clearly we get absurdities and it justifies the fact that we do not have polygons with sides 1 and 2. For $n=3,4,6$ one gets the ratio as 6, 4 and 3 respectively. But for any other value of n , one can check that we end up with a non-integral positive number. Hence the only regular polygons that tessellate the Euclidean plane \mathbf{E}^2 are the equilateral triangle, the square and the regular hexagon. The hyperbolic plane \mathbf{H}^2 came into existence when people began questioning Euclid's fifth axiom.

The theory of Fuchsian groups helps us not only decide tessellations of \mathbf{H}^2 but also of the quotients which lead to Riemann surfaces S of genus $g \geq 2$.

We have mentioned in the beginning of this section that any orientable closed surface can be complexified and hence appealing to the uniformization theorem described above we have the following.

Proposition(1.2) Let S be an open surface or a smooth orientable closed surface. Then there exists a tessellation of S describable by group acting discretely on S .

We have already seen the tessellation of the plane. The abstract group that corresponds to one such tessellation namely the square tilings is by the action of $\mathbf{Z} \times \mathbf{Z}$ on the plane \mathbf{R}^2 .

On any compact Riemann surface of genus $g > 2$ one can compute certain groups of conformal automorphisms whose actions correspond to hyperbolic tessellations.

Similarly the rhombic polyhedral filling [2] out the 3-space \mathbf{R}^3 is realized by a group presented by three elements f, g, h viz $G = \langle f, g, h \rangle$ where $f(x) = x + I$, $g(x) = x + j$ and $h(x) = x + k$ where x is any point in the space and i, j, k are elements of the standard basis of \mathbf{R}^3 .

II. PLATONIC TESSELLATIONS

A tessellation of a Riemann surface is called platonic if the group action of the symmetries is transitive on flags of faces, edges and vertices. A Platonic Riemann surface is one on which one can put platonic tessellations. We use again group theoretic language to describe platonic tessellations. For genus zero surfaces we have the regular polyhedra while for genus-1 surfaces we have the well known description of tilings by fundamental parallelograms. For compact Riemann surfaces of genus $g \geq 2$, we have techniques from hyperbolic geometry. Thus to every member in the classification of closed Riemann surfaces one can associate a tessellation.

The Hyperbolic plane and its tessellation:

The upper half plane \mathbf{H} is biholomorphic to the unit disk and it has a well understood topology and geometry using the Poincare metric.

The topological space \mathbf{H} is acted upon by the projective linear group $\text{PSL}(2, \mathbf{R})$. This action is transitive since for any pair of points $\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2 \in \mathbf{H}$, \exists a symmetry $\sigma \in \text{PSL}(2, \mathbf{R})$ such that $\sigma(\mathbf{z}_1) = \mathbf{z}_2$, thus making \mathbf{H} a homogeneous space. Now one can classify isometries of \mathbf{H} under the action of suitable discrete subgroups of $\text{PSL}(2, \mathbf{R})$. Let Γ be one such group. Since the fixed point equation for any transformation t in Γ is $\Gamma(z) = z$, we have the following equation

$$cz^2 + (d-a)z - b = 0$$

Using the standard formulation of fractional linear transformations, based on the roots of the quadratic equation (1) one can classify any transformation as

- 1) Elliptic
- 2) Parabolic
- 3) Hyperbolic.

Observing the matrix topology of $\text{PSL}(2, \mathbf{R})$ one deduces that if $\Gamma \subset \text{PSL}(2, \mathbf{R})$ then $\Gamma \backslash \mathbf{H}$ is a Riemann surface, furthermore a Fuchsian group acts discontinuously on \mathbf{H} and Γ has no elliptic points. Thus we have the following result:

Proposition(2.1) Any Fuchsian group leads to a tessellated Riemann surface and conversely for any Riemann surface S of genus $g \geq 2$ there exists a Fuchsian group such that $\Gamma \backslash \mathbf{H}$ diffeomorphic to S .

In fact in the special case of platonic tessellations the fundamental domain or *tile* is the hyperbolic triangle of the type $(2, k, 1)$. In other words the angles of the fundamental domain which is a hyperbolic triangle are $\pi/2$, π/k , and $\pi/1$ respectively. The associated group action is that of a hyperbolic triangle group. This group is generated by the reflections in

the edges of the $(2,k,1)$ triangles.

Arithmetic considerations and related combinatorics.

The idea of arithmetic arising in case of manifold constructions goes back to the concept of geometry of numbers as propounded by H.Minkowski. This study was taken up more seriously after David Hilbert proposed among his famous 23 problems in the year 1900, the problems concerning crystallographic groups. In fact in the 17th century Kepler did initiate the algebraic theory for packing problems in space.

In [13] the author considers the triangle groups which we discussed above in the setting of the discrete subgroups Γ of the group $\mathbf{PSL}(2,\mathbf{R})$ and associated hyperbolic tilings and they develop a theory of related combinatorial structures. In particular the group $\Gamma = \mathbf{PSL}(2,\mathbf{Z})$ is considered and a 1-1 correspondence between conjugacy classes of subgroups of finite index in Γ and certain bipartite cuboid graphs is established. These graphs are constructed arithmetically using Farey symbols and hence associated Riemann surfaces can be given tilings by the so called “special polygons” as described in [RS]. A special polygon mentioned therein is a convex polygon of finite hyperbolic area in \mathbf{H} which is made up of tiles of an extended modular tessellation. Hence every subgroup of finite index in Γ admits a special polygon as a fundamental polygon.

More combinatorial structures in the setting of Riemann surfaces can be seen in literature. Ribbon graphs are introduced to study families of Riemann surfaces using techniques from topological graph theory and algebraic geometry. Robert Penner had introduced the fat graphs which are technically ribbon graphs associated to Riemann surfaces with boundary.

In another direction the works of Belyi, Grothendieck and others describe combinatorial structures similar to the ones described above. A dessin d’enfant is a graph embedded on an oriented surface such that the embedding has faces which are topological discs and surrounding each vertex is

a cyclic order of edges. Circle patterns are used in discrete differential geometric setting to build hyperbolic surfaces. By using modular groups the above mentioned patterns lead to polyhedral meshes. Since all of these examples are associated to the hyperbolic plane one can get combinatorial structures for such geometric spaces in higher dimensions.

III.POSSIBLE GENERALIZATIONS TO HIGHER DIMENSIONS

Describing such tessellations in higher dimensions involves complications due to the non- availability of uniformizations. However on flat manifolds of certain kind Bieberbach’s theorem from crystallography guarantees tessellations of the kind that we have looked at i.e involving number theory and

discrete group structures. The idea is the following: According to the above mentioned theorem any n -dimensional crystallographic group Γ contains n - linearly independent parallel translations; the group G of linear parts of the transformations from Γ is finite. Bieberbach theorem yields the following description of the structure of crystallographic groups as abstract groups. Let L be the set of all parallel translations in a crystallographic group Γ . Then L is a normal subgroup of finite index, isomorphic to \mathbf{Z}_n , and is its own centralizer in Γ . The existence of a normal subgroup L of an abstract group Γ possessing these properties is a sufficient condition for Γ to be isomorphic to a crystallographic group. The group G of linear parts of a crystallographic group Γ preserves the lattice L ; in other words, relative to a basis of L the transformations in G are represented by matrices with integer entries.

In summary covering space theory allows one to look at group actions on Euclidean model spaces and the corresponding quotient structures lead to compact spaces which get an induced tessellation. There is a natural tessellation of the flat torus and Bieberbach's result implies that every compact Riemannian manifold is covered by a flat torus. The kind of isometries that we have considered lead to lattices in \mathbf{R}^n or \mathbf{C}^n as the case may be. Further using Minkowski's geometry of numbers one can construct interesting lattices and the theory therein lead us into interesting geometric estimates using Arithmetic geometry.

In [14] homogeneous group actions are described leading to some nice tessellations but generalising the same to arbitrary manifolds is far from trivial. But in case of 3-manifolds and 4-manifolds atleast in the case of Siefert fibered manifolds the above speculations can be made precise. A manifold is called as Siefert fibered if it admits a foliation by circles. That is it has a decomposition into disjoint union of circles. So for any such Siefert fibered space there is a well known theory as to how to obtain nice tessellations.

Also in dimension-2 all possible crystallographic groups (totally 17 in number) are identified. Now flat 2-orbifolds can be bases for Seifert fibered 3-manifolds and 4-manifolds. But each 2-orbifold can be tessellated by the group theoretic arguments of section-2. It is our hope that a classification of possible tessellations in the above mentioned special cases can be obtained using certain z -classes.

IV. SOME APPLICATIONS

In this section we collect details of some applications of the discretizations that we have defined. Basically it is the focus that curvatures of shapes are captured in a discrete format through the combinatorial structures that we referred to. Since crystal patterns are our basic observations, this formulation applies to materials that have a regular lattice structure.

Further *Tessellations* are referred in the professional areas of architectural designs and graphic designs. Both these professional fields are now using digital techniques. In fact a whole new subject of discrete differential geometry has emerged to help such designers. The basic blocks being points, triangles

tetrahedral and such primitives, digital models are rendered mathematically as simplicial complexes thus using the language of algebraic topology. So the methods mentioned in this paper are useful for procedures like automatic digitization and numerical techniques like segmentation and mesh compression. It is common nowadays that complex analytic frameworks involving Mobius functions on complexified geometric shapes are used for two dimensional and three dimensional surface rendering. In another direction wall paper symmetries in Alhambra (Spain) shows that ornamental patterns challenged artistes even in the medieval periods. Mesh descriptions of architectural designs adopt quadrilateral, triangular or hexagonal meshes which can be mathematically viewed as tessellations. Improvisations on such structures are often made by simulations involving groups of symmetries. In artistic graphics design 2-dimensional and 3-dimensional illusions are essentially created by motivations from projective geometry and related 'geometric structures'. Finally in mechanics Discrete fibres play an important role especially in quantum physics and associated numerical schemes where the base manifolds of fiber bundles need to be appropriately discretised.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A.F.Beardon, The Geometry of Discrete Groups, Springer-Verlag, 1995.
- [2] Alan Holden, Shapes, Space and Symmetry. Dover Books, 1971, vol. 61.
- [3] A.Jose, Montesinos, "Classical Tessellations and three manifolds Springer-Verlag, 1987.
- [4] B.Grunbaum, "What symmetry groups are present in the Alhambra?" in Notices, AMS, Vol53 # 6, 2006.
- [5] Bobenko, A., Hoffmann, T., Springborn, B, "Minimal surfaces from circle patterns: Geometry from combinatorics," Ann. of Math, 164, pp231 – 264.2006.
- [6] Barret.O'Neil, "Elementary Differential Geometry", Academic Press NY 2006.
- [7] Corn D, Singerman D, "Regular Hypermaps", European Journ Combin, 9, 1988
- [8] H.Hiller, "Crystallography and Cohomology of Groups", American Math Monthly, Vol 93, #10, 1986.
- [9] James R.Munkres, "Topology A First Course", Prentice Hall of India 1996,
- [10] Jones, Singerman D, , "Belyi functions, Hypermaps and Galois Groups", Bull, London Math Soc.,#28, 1996.
- [11] Reiner Kuhnau, , "Handbook of Complex Analysis: Complex Function theory", Vol 2, 2005.
- [12] Robin Hartshorne, "Basic Algebraic Geometry" , Springer-Verlag, 1986.
- [13] R.S.Kulkarni, "An arithmetic-geometric method in the study of the subgroups of the modular group," Amer. Journ of Math, Vol 113, #6, pp 1053-1133, 1991.
- [14] W.Boothby, "An Introduction to Differentiable manifolds and Riemannian Geometry," Academic Press, 1975.
- [15] William Thurston, "The geometry and Topology of three manifolds," Preprint.